

The (partial) communication of sport

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The most popular sports and those with the greatest economic investment have more space in the media, while others are only minimally covered, i.e. there are imbalances when comparing the number and variety of practices in the news.

Sustained processes of dissemination of all competences have not yet been achieved. Moreover, the collective has more viewers than the individual, and undoubtedly demands high volumes of data.

The communication of sport and its institutions is restricted to topics close to spectacle, crisis or fatalities, but life stories, post-professional stages, seedlings and grassroots championships are almost absent from the news. This is changing, however, thanks to the triumphs of Paris 2024, which show that there are other routes to success that are not in the frequent perspectives of published information.

Sport is virtue, vocation, daily exercise and a way of life that brings out the best in individuals and families. It is also a team commitment to achieve excellence.

It remains to build a communication that shows and educates the population to understand that along with football, wrestling or car racing there are other areas. Hopefully the editors, both online and traditional media, will continue to provide opportunities for young people in those disciplines that have received little, but that give a lot for Ecuador to have a place on the Olympic map.